

Shaping a new model of mental health care: Leveraging conversational agents as collateral informants

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Abstract

Access to evidence-informed mental health care is throttled at the front door by slow triage, repetitive forms, long waits, and rising costs, compounded by clinician shortages. Meanwhile, hundreds of millions of people now use general-purpose chatbots for reflection and advice, tools that can help but also mirror, mislead, or erode safety without clinical guardrails. To address this growing gap between rapid AI adoption and responsible clinical practice, we argue for a clinician-anchored model that uses AI to accelerate access while preserving judgement and trust. As a first step, we introduce Chapter, a narrative-based intake that pairs validated patient-reported outcomes with the patient story across functional domains to produce a concise, context-rich pre-visit brief. To complement this, we introduce Fillm™, which allows patients to selectively transform parts of their prior chatbot conversations into labeled collateral for clinician review. Together, these tools aim to reduce time-to-care, improve first-session readiness, and strengthen early alliance without permitting algorithm-only decisions. Our position is that AI should enhance, not replace, human care. Chatbots can accelerate time-to-care from mental health assessment to treatment, but with clinicians firmly in the loop to ensure safety and preserve human connection.

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1 Introduction

Untreated or under-treated mental health conditions in the US cost nearly \$478 billion per year; Deloitte’s 2025 forecast puts that burden above \$1.3 trillion annually by 2040. The largest barrier to appropriate treatment is the front door bottleneck, which includes slow triage, paperwork, wait-lists, and rising co-pays exacerbated by clinician shortages. In response to these barriers, many have turned to AI-based conversational agents (CAs). While they promise fast, easily available support, accessible 24/7, they also raise new challenges. Most consumer chatbots today act as mirrors, they echo users’ words, provide overly agreeable and even unsafe advice, and may deter patients from seeking evidence-informed treatment. (Rafkova and Voronin, 2025).

Access to mental health care remains a significant challenge, leaving many without the support they need to manage their well-being. Forty-six percent of individuals with mental health challenges do not receive the care that they need (Health Resources and Services Administration (HRSA), 2024). Before people even reach a provider, they encounter initial barriers such as high costs, limited provider directories, and geographic shortages of clinicians. These factors discourage many from seeking care at all. For those who persist, a second layer of obstacles emerges at the “front door” of care, during screening and intake. The median wait for an in-person psychiatry appointment is 67 days, and even tele-psychiatry averages six weeks (Sun et al., 2023). Federal workforce reports corroborate a 48-day average wait for behavioral-health appointments across disciplines (Health Resources and Services Administration (HRSA), 2024). When patients reach the “front door,” there can be further obstacles to finding evidence-informed care and appropriate clinical fit. Time required to seek care is a primary barrier to accessing mental health care, resulting in lost income and presenting challenges with return-to-work policies. The economic and individual costs of missing work to approach the front door of care are very high. Moreover, insurance co-pays can exceed \$150 per session, compounding the delay with affordability barriers, exacerbating already existing health disparities. Together, these frictions force many would-be patients to self-triage or abandon care altogether.

As of August 2024, more than 122 million Americans, over one-third of the population, live in Mental Health Professional Shortage Areas (HPSAs) (Health Resources and Services Administration (HRSA), 2024). The maldistribution is significant, with rural counties likelier to have zero practicing psychiatrists, leaving primary-care clinicians to shoulder complex mental-health caseloads. Provider burnout, narrow reimbursement constraints, and regulatory limitations on scope-of-practice contribute to a decreasing supply of qualified clinicians coinciding with surges in demand for mental health care. Against this backdrop of limited access and clinician shortages, technology has begun to fill the gaps in how people seek mental health support.

Our approach centers on two complementary methods designed to improve the assessment process, accelerate access to care and deepen the therapeutic alliance between clinician and patient. The first, called Chapter, is a narrative-

based assessment framework that shortens the time from initial presentation to meaningful clinical engagement from weeks to hours. By moving beyond symptom checklists and direct self-report, this framework captures the nuances of lived experience, revealing patterns that inform more focused and higher-quality clinical encounters. Through structured narrative elicitation, it restores one of the most valuable aspects of mental-health practice which is the ability to form connections rooted in a deep understanding of each patient’s story.

Complementing this framework, the second method, called Fillm™, is a secure way to enable patients to share reflections and summaries generated through their conversations with AI agents, directly within their clinical assessment. Patients retain full agency in deciding what to include, and all shared content is provided to clinicians in a structured format. By integrating this patient-permissioned data into Chapter, Fillm™ expands the clinician’s view to a more holistic understanding of functioning and context. These methods address a critical moment in the evolution of mental health care.

Increasingly, individuals turn to AI-based conversational agents for reflection, emotional regulation, and advice. While such tools can provide accessible entry points for self-exploration, their unstructured and unguided use also introduces risks related to misinformation, privacy, and safety. Embedding these technologies within clinician-governed intake workflows channels their potential toward clinical benefit, ensuring that AI supports rather than substitutes the therapeutic process.

2 Rising chatbot use, a new social behavior

With the advent of ChatGPT, Claude, and other AI conversational tools, people are using chatbots more widely for reflection and companionship. This is not a niche trend, but rather a mass behavioral shift, a new kind of social behavior, quietly reshaping how people seek, test, and trust sources of support. They come not just for facts, but for comfort, reflection, even vulnerability. Every week, roughly 400 million people interact with ChatGPT, about 60 % of the entire generative-AI chatbot market (Phang et al., 2025). Large-scale log analysis shows that approximately three percent of exchanges with Claude are “affective”, involving counselling, interpersonal advice, or companionship (McCain et al., 2025). High chatbot usage has been associated with emotional dependence on the chatbot (Phang et al., 2025). We live in an asynchronous world where people can and often need to address their needs on the go. This behavioral shift presents potential therapeutic value for extending mental health support through technology, but it also exposes patients to risks of overreliance on CAs, which we address next.

In contrast to commercial CAs, generative AI tools developed intentionally for therapy by scientists and mental health professionals have promise for specific purposes such as early detection of mental health symptoms (e.g. diagnosis using cues like tone of voice, word choice, and speech patterns), treatment plans tailored to the patient, and AI-driven CAs designed for therapy (Olawade

et al., 2024). A randomized controlled trial examining the use of a generative AI therapy-specific CA for adults with major depressive disorder or generalized anxiety disorder was associated with reductions in both depression and anxiety symptoms (Heinz et al., 2025). Regardless of the application, we need guardrails to maintain ethics and safety. Parks and colleagues (Parks et al., 2025) propose five criteria to critically evaluate chatbots for mental health: ethics (justice and fairness, promoting autonomy), safety (clear guardrails for the CA’s behavior), accessibility (considering factors like language and health literacy), evidence-based (grounded in science), and application of core coaching skills (e.g., therapeutic alliance and empathy). Employing human-in-the-loop and human review processes is critical in the development of these tools to meet these criteria.

3 Risks of Overreliance on CAs

Although direct-to-consumer CAs give patients wide access to support with unconditional positive regard, which can be beneficial, there is potential for harm. Findings from a systematic review on CAs for mental health demonstrated that use of CAs was associated with improvement in symptoms of depression and general distress, but no changes were found in overall psychological well-being (Li et al., 2023). On the other hand, there is heightened risk in seeking support from AI-driven CAs, particularly for those who are already vulnerable due to an underlying mental health condition (Gao, 2024). Turning to a commercial chatbot as a therapist comes with risks such as data privacy concerns with sensitive mental health information, have inherent biases (e.g., race- and gender-based biases), and can present real safety concerns (Li et al., 2023). There have been documented instances of chatbots encouraging self-harm or colluding with delusions (Stewart et al., 2025).

Beyond that, these interactions can promote unrealistic relationship expectations without therapeutic boundaries. These risks often stem from how CAs are designed to interact, with patterns of mirroring and excessive agreeableness that can reinforce distorted thinking or unsafe behaviors. To sustain engagement, many CA models default to overly agreeable, praise-heavy replies lacking authenticity (e.g., OpenAI (2025)) providing false reassurance rather than clinically sound guidance. Researchers recently found that chatbot models trained to be warm and empathic are less reliable, particularly when users respond with emotional context such as sadness (Ibrahim et al., 2025). This tendency to be sycophantic and excessively supportive in a disingenuous manner with patients’ beliefs even if they are false undermines trust (Carro, 2024). Furthermore, CAs often echo the user’s own language and tone, which can unintentionally reinforce distorted thinking or self-harm ideation instead of challenging it. When CAs ‘self-disclose,’ users often reveal more, which can intensify negative emotions when chatbots act as a mirror (Chaturvedi et al., 2023). CAs can create parasocial relationships with users. This type of friendship can encourage human engagement, yet these interactions validate what users say and model conflict avoidance, thereby creating unrealistic expectations for relationships. This re-

flective tendency can feel comforting to the user but often results in the CAs affirming false beliefs and offering unsafe advice.

Some AI-based tools market themselves as stand-alone substitutes for therapy, diverting users from the human connection and nuanced clinical judgment that underpin mental health care. A more effective role for AI is at the front door (i.e., for screening and intake), where this technology can reduce bottlenecks (Gorelik et al., 2025). Today, far more people use general-purpose CAs than clinically validated therapeutic tools, largely because chatbots are more widely accessible than evidence-based apps and human clinicians. While communicating with a CA can provide short-term relief (e.g., venting), its benefits diminish over time and carry risks. In contrast, when applied alongside human-based care, CAs can enhance mental health support at both the assessment stage and through ongoing monitoring. Realizing AI’s potential at the front door requires rethinking intake design so it captures the nuance of each patient’s story.

4 Why intake must evolve

Most screening tools still rely on sterile, clinical checklists and scales that flatten the person into a list of symptoms, losing the context and nuance behind the personal story. Intake forms rarely reflect how people talk about their mental health. Existing assessments do not consider the style, tone, or depth of reflection that patients may already be engaging in conversations with AI. There is a growing gap between how people express themselves and how systems are listening. We believe this is a missed opportunity. Intake should meet patients where they are, not just in terms of accessibility, but in language, tempo, and the kinds of self-awareness tools they are already using. The next generation of behavioral health systems will not solely ask better questions they will improve understanding of how people are already answering them elsewhere. When the way people ask for help evolves, our intake forms cannot stay frozen in time. A meaningful slice of conversations with commercial AI chatbots are not about coding or travel tips; they cover stress, anxiety, grief, and relationship conflict (Phang et al., 2025). In other words, millions now rehearse their most personal narratives with an AI-based CA before they ever speak to a clinician. Yet most behavioral-health screening and intake still look and feel like they were designed for an analog era, relying on outdated tools such as:

- Symptom checklists that ignore context. “Rate your mood today” does not reveal how someone’s friendships have deteriorated or how they show up at work.
- Binary risk flags instead of nuanced stories. A single “yes” to suicidal thoughts can trigger protocol yet miss the loneliness or existential drift that preceded it.
- Static, one-way intake forms. Patients pour their feelings into CAs because

they “listen” in real time. Our intake portals, by contrast, often reply with silence.

The result is a widening gap between how people now disclose distress and how clinicians first encounter them. We are meeting a new generation of self-reflective, tech-native patients with static paper forms. This gap is important to understand, as behavioral health is fundamentally relational. Therapeutic alliance starts the moment a patient decides, “this person gets me.” If intake feels detached and sterile, that moment never arrives and traction is lost before the first appointment, leading to attrition and underutilized capacity. A socially aware and human-centered intake mirrors real conversation. For example, inquiring “What have you been talking about with friends or with AI when you can’t sleep?” Intake should capture signals beyond symptoms, including changes in social roles, attachment patterns, and digital help-seeking.

Updating forms is not glamorous, but it is decisive. Intake is the first handshake; it can feel either sterile or empathic. If we claim to treat the whole person, the process that welcomes them must capture the parts that matter most, how they connect, withdraw, text at any time, or confide in a CA. The task is simple but urgent: design screening that reflects the reality that we are social creatures living in a digital world. When our questions honor the way patients already tell their stories, the real work of healing begins one step earlier and much stronger. Changing how we initiate care is only part of the solution. To make these changes meaningful, we must root them in a deeper understanding of the psychological and contextual factors that shape mental health.

5 Toward Human-Centered, AI-Enhanced Care

As we recognize the need for a new approach to assessment that captures the whole person, we draw on transdiagnostic approaches to psychopathology—factors underlying the mental health challenges our patients face. Frameworks like Hierarchical Taxonomy of Psychopathology (Cicero et al., 2024; Kotov et al., 2017) and concepts such as the P-factor (Carver et al., 2017) go beyond diagnosis and focus on how underlying factors such as disinhibition or impulsive responsiveness impact function. For example, HiTOP adds value by accommodating comorbidity (DeYoung et al., 2023). Moreover, these underlying factors have treatment implications (e.g., ability to engage in treatment). Importantly, these cross-cutting models account for contextual factors such as chronic stress contributing to the transdiagnostic process due to racial discrimination and oppression and allow our provision of care to be contextually appropriate and culturally responsive in turn.

These transdiagnostic frameworks can serve as a foundation of a more holistic, human-centered assessment, yet these models are complex. Ultimately people care about functioning within our context because this speaks to how we show up at work, in relationships, and for ourselves. We can leverage the power of AI to get at the complexity and context underlying a patient’s presenting

concerns. Assessments should capture the whole person, so that the patient’s story is summarized in a narrative way so they will not have to expend energy recapitulating their story to each provider over the course of their care journey. This allows the patient to be seen and enhance the therapeutic connection and depth of therapeutic work, understanding, and insight.

A significant benefit of AI technologies is their ability to bridge the gap between research and practice, specifically by facilitating the widespread adoption of dimensional models of mental health disorders. These technologies could make leading evidence-based models of mental health case conceptualization generally accessible, which are currently only utilized by a small percentage of specialists (Gorelik et al., 2025). Models such as HiTOP were developed for research contexts and are complex to apply in routine care. AI can help translate these frameworks into usable formats for clinicians.

AI chatbots (commercial CAs) as informants can add valuable collateral to the holistic view of a patient’s narrative. In general, gathering collateral information from others close to your patient, or leveraging technology that they regularly interact with, informants can be beneficial for transdiagnostic assessment of psychopathology but also personality characteristics more broadly, as well as aiding understanding of intersectional identities (Eaton, 2020). For instance, with a CA as an informant you can learn about your patients’ language patterns potentially indicative of underlying mental health concerns and general patterns of behavior and personality. With richer information, providers can gain further insight into a patient’s vulnerabilities such as patterns of internalizing, externalizing, detaching. Using a CA as standalone source is not helpful but combining it with narrative assessment to capture whole mental health story is valuable.

At the same time, the broader integration of generative AI into mental health care presents both significant promise and critical risks. We recognize that these technologies are increasingly being used by individuals seeking support, clarity, and connection. While we know that CAs can respond in a warm and reflective way, **we believe they are not a replacement for professional mental health services or medical opinion and should not serve as such.**

6 Our position

The question is not whether to use AI in mental health, but how. Our position is clear that AI should serve as a bridge, not a replacement. We advocate leveraging the power of this rapidly evolving technology to expand access to empathic, evidence-informed mental health care. This means using generative AI tools to support front-end processes such as screening and intake, reducing bottlenecks and administrative burden, and moving patients more efficiently from first contact to therapeutic engagement. The result is greater access to appropriate care, especially for those deterred by long waits, complex intake, or high costs. AI can serve as a bridge between distress and care, but it should never be the endpoint. This means building workflows that are emotionally

attuned and accessible, while grounded in clinical infrastructure to ensure safety and continuity. Clinicians can use AI to create whole-person narratives rather than single scores on a screener, guided by dimensional models such as HiTOP and the p-factor.

Critical to this vision are human-in-the-loop (HITL) systems where expert review is embedded at key stages such as data labeling, model tuning, evaluation, deployment oversight, and continuous feedback loops (Holzinger, 2016). The core advantage comes from complementarity. AI handles scale, throughput, consistency, and pattern finding across large data, while clinicians contribute nuanced contextual insight, ethical judgment, and interpretive flexibility under real-world constraints. In practice, AI can draft intake summaries, suggest schedules, generate billing codes for clinicians to approve, or support patients through tools like Fillm™, where reflections collected by AI can inform therapy sessions. In all cases, human review remains essential to ensure that sensitive decisions are never ceded to the algorithm. When designed right, HITL systems do not displace clinicians but extend their reach, compensating for human limits while safeguarding judgment. This balance underscores why collaboration between AI researchers and clinical scientists is no longer optional but indispensable. HITL AI tools in screening and intake illustrate a promising bridge, enabling patient narratives to be structured and contextualized in ways that reflect both clinical judgment and algorithmic efficiency.

7 Our solution

We have outlined the challenges, risks, and guiding principles for the role of AI in mental health. Our solution is built on two practical tools that translate these principles into practice. In particular, Chapter is a narrative-based assessment that combines validated patient-reported outcome measures (PROs) with structured elicitation of functional domains (work, relationships, social support etc.) through direct and indirect self-report, producing a concise pre-visit brief that clinicians can act on during session one. In addition, Fillm™ lets patients selectively share reflections from personal CAs. These can be summarised, safety-screened, and presented as labelled collateral for clinician review. Together, Chapter and Fillm™ reduce repetitive form-filling, improve clinician–patient fit, and accelerate time-to-care while protecting privacy and maintaining a clear human-in-the-loop boundary. Read more about Chapter and Fillm™ here ¹.

Together, Chapter and Fillm™ deliver clear benefits across the care pathway. For patients they reduce forms and repetition, speeding up appointments, and fostering the experience of being truly seen. For clinicians, they provide pre-visit insights, lowering administrative burden, improving patient-clinician fit, and freeing-up more time for therapeutic work. Finally, for health systems, Chapter and Fillm™ facilitate shorter queues, decreasing no-show rates, and ensuring clearer documentation that supports continuity and accountability. The result is a clinician-anchored, technology-enabled system that does not

¹<https://psychnow.com/chapter>

replace human care but instead expands access, ensures safety, and maintains the human connection at the core of mental health treatment.

8 Call to action

Adopt a human-centred, clinician-in-the-loop front door that speeds access without sacrificing judgement. Use Chapter to turn intake into a concise, context-rich brief and Fillm™ to convert patient-permissioned CA reflections into labelled collateral. Start from the tools patients already trust, but channel them safely with clinicians in the loop. Build ethics and privacy in by design, with data minimisation, clear auditability, and revocable controls. And never allow algorithm-only clinical decisions: AI assists, clinicians interpret, decide, and document.

9 Conclusion

AI at the “front door” of mental health should shorten the path to meaningful care without diluting clinical judgement, privacy, or trust. With Chapter, patients tell their story once, in their words, aligned to validated measures and functional domains. With Fillm™, they can turn selected chatbot reflections into collateral information for clinician review. We reject algorithm-only triage and commit to human-in-the-loop governance, data minimization and transparent provenance. We aim to modernise access while keeping clinicians and human connection at the center of care.

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